

ELECTRIC FORKLIFT TRUCKS REFURBISHMENT AT S.C. JUNGHEINRICH RECONDITIONARE ROMANIA S.R.L.

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Abstract

Purpose – developing an electric forklift trucks refurbishment business in 2022 in Ploiesti in a period of hyperinflation generated by the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, with German managerial know-how and lower costs of local suppliers.

Methodology/approach – conducting a SWOT and ESG analysis of the refurbishment business, a CO₂ emissions comparison between diesel-powered and electric forklift trucks with lead-acid and lithium-ion batteries.

Findings – Refurbishing electric forklift trucks extends their life cycle by 94 percent and saves around 80 percent of CO₂ emissions compared to new production. An electric forklift truck with lithium-ion battery emits 52 percent less CO₂ than a diesel-powered forklift truck.

Research limitations/implications – the research is limited to SWOT and ESG analysis and internal documents provided by the company with implications for the local economy development.

Practical implications – Jungstars brand lithium-ion battery electric forklift trucks refurbishment business offers sustainable and resource-efficient solutions, the resulting equipment looking and performing as good as new.

Originality/value – the main author of this paper, as an employee of the purchasing department, actively participated in the opening of this new forklift trucks refurbishment plant, looking for local suppliers needed for the smooth running of the business.

Key words: Jungheinrich, refurbishment, lithium-ion.

Introduction

The centralised industrial refurbishment is the basis of the used equipment business and ensures that used forklift trucks become Jungheinrich Jungstars, a benchmark for the used forklift trucks industry. The refurbishment has many benefits for the customer and for us (e.g., Blind and Hipp, 2003; Lindahl, Sundin and Östlin, 2006; Lindahl et al., 2006; Helfat et al., 2007; Boșcoianu, Prelipcean and Lupan, 2018; Makaryan, Hoppe and Fortuin, 2022).

The refurbishment of used forklift trucks involves a centralised uniform procedure in six separate steps: incoming inspection on arrival, disassembly, surface work, component refurbishment, assembly and final inspection. Throughout the entire process each step is strictly quality controlled to ensure the highest level of safety and reliability. The cost and benefits of Jungstars are unbeatable, with lower costs and higher customer satisfaction.

Table 1. The steps of the Jungheinrich electric forklift trucks refurbishment process

Steps	Description
Initial inspection on arrival	During the arrival inspection, the condition of the forklift truck is determined All safety components and worn components such as wheels, chains and hoses are always replaced with original spare parts
Disassembly	The arrival inspection is followed by disassembly and thorough cleaning Consumables such as brake fluid, engine oil and hydraulic oil are disposed of in accordance with environmental regulations
Surface work	The truck frame and mast are primed, smoothed and painted Following inspection and any necessary repairs, the overhead guard, steering system, sideshift, tilt cylinders and battery are blasted and repainted
Component refurbishment	Depending on the forklift truck type, the wheels and spring elements are replaced, the pull rods and axles are overhauled and new bearings and bolts are inserted The transmissions and engines are overhauled and wearing parts are changed The masts are disassembled and the hoses and chains are replaced The batteries are refurbished or replaced
Assembly	The frame, mast and any components are put back together and the forklift truck is restored The finished forklift truck is now as good as new
Final inspection	The final inspection is then carried out by means of a functional test with nominal load. Each forklift truck leaves the industrial refurbishment process as a premium-quality Jungheinrich Jungstar with a safety certificate and personal quality promise from the responsible engineer

The SWOT and ESG analysis of Jungheinrich electric forklift trucks refurbishment

We will conduct a SWOT and an ESG analysis (e.g., Gürel and Akkoç, 2011; Gillan, Koch and Starks, 2021). In the SWOT analysis we will highlight the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the electric forklift trucks refurbishment business. The strengths are internal positive elements, the weaknesses are internal negative elements, the opportunities are external positive elements and the threats are external negative elements (Table 2). In the ESG analysis we will highlight the environmental, social and corporate governance factors of the electric forklift trucks refurbishment business (Table 3).

Table 2. The SWOT analysis of Jungheinrich electric forklift trucks refurbishment

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Opening of a new state-of-the-art factory Premium quality used electric forklift trucks Look like new and are as good as new Own brand – Jungstars The five-star principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety - Technology - Appearance - Reliability - Sustainability <p>The first forklift trucks refurbishment company Complete intralogistics solutions and services Standardised procedure and highest standards Experienced staff the strictest quality controls Replaced safety-relevant components Centralised uniform and total refurbishment Complete disassembly and original spare parts Reduced consumption of energy and materials Cheaper than a new equipment Trade-in for each used machine</p>	<p>Presence of factories in few countries Growth below market potential Not all components are replaced Second-hand equipment Lower quality than new equipment Wears out faster than new equipment Shorter lifetime than new equipment Lower warranty than for a new product The financial services attached involve interest Excessive standardisation creates rigidity Centralisation takes extra time</p>

<p>Test drive in the subsidiary Flexible and personalised financial services Customer focus and customized solutions Active selling and after-sales service 94 percent reuse rate per truck 80 percent CO₂ emissions saved 12 months warranty and maintenance-free 10 days right of return</p>	
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Opening more refurbishment plants Transition from fossil fuels to electricity Transition from lead-acid to lithium-ion batteries Increasing demand for refurbished equipment Limited budget and price-sensitive customers Sustainability concerned customers Low to medium usage times customers Mixed fleet customers High levels of wear and tough use customers Customers working in a single shift Start-ups and small companies Suitable for rental and stand-by solutions Resource-saving and energy-saving policies Minimizing the use of new parts Ensuring the highest quality standards Investment in research and development Cost savings in the context of rising inflation Extend product life cycle by two to three times All new forklift trucks can be refurbished European Green Deal provisions National Recovery and Resilience Plan projects</p>	<p>Coronavirus pandemic Outbreak of war Disruption of supply chains Cheaper competition price with lower quality The competitors offer different levels of quality No complete disassembly from competition Regional workshop refurbishment Increased bureaucracy High initial investment Not suitable for customers working three shifts Limited natural resources Shortage of skilled labour Scarcity of modern industrial services High initial prices of some local suppliers Generalized cost increases Competition from emerging countries</p>

Table 3. The ESG analysis of Jungheinrich electric forklift trucks refurbishment

Environmental
<p>Environmentally conscious customers Saves around 80 percent CO₂ emissions compared to new production Electric forklift trucks emit less CO₂ than diesel-powered forklift trucks Lithium-ion batteries emit less CO₂ than lead-acid batteries Reduced natural resources consumption Limited resources will stimulate refurbishment Environmentally friendly technologies are more expensive Electric transport is the technology of the future The European Green Deal requirements are implemented Contributes to the energy independence of logistics platforms Ensures the transition from fossil fuels to electricity Use of renewable energy and modern green technologies will reduce global warming</p>
Social
<p>Lower costs in an inflationary period caused by the coronavirus pandemic and the war in Ukraine Increasing population health by reducing pollution Unemployment will be generated in the diesel-powered forklift trucks industry Sustainable new jobs will be created in the electric forklift trucks refurbishment industry More jobs to come in the battery and electric charging station industry Bottlenecks in the supply chain will be reduced by increasing the speed of movement of goods Economic growth will increase social cohesion Increased demand for quality products will increase the welfare of the population The use of refurbished equipment leads to lower end-product costs Expanding business in developing countries will help reduce poverty</p>

Corporate governance

The first industrial company which refurbished logistics equipment
 Buy-back facility offered for used forklift trucks
 Multinational organizational culture and German managerial know-how implemented in Romania
 Investment in research and development of new technologies such as lithium-ion batteries
 Equipment refurbishment and long-term use of batteries contribute significantly to sustainability
 Reducing resource consumption through automation of processes
 Purchasing the best materials and access to relatively cheap local resources
 Increased production will lead to economies of scale
 Market research to identify customer needs
 Implementation of the "think global, act local" principle
 Ensuring the highest quality standards through total and centralised refurbishment
 The refurbishment of electric forklift trucks will evolve towards re-refurbishment

An energy efficiency analysis of electric forklift trucks in terms of CO₂ emissions

The Jungheinrich product eco balance considers the CO₂ emissions during the manufacture, production, use and processing/recycling of all products. In addition to the certified Jungheinrich Product Life Cycle Assessment, the calculation is based on a 2017 study by the Swedish Environmental Research Institute with valid information on CO₂ emissions during the manufacture and recycling of lithium-ion cells. The calculation is based on a service life of 10.000 operating hours of a 2,5 tons forklift truck and the current EU electricity mix for calculating CO₂ emissions from electricity generation (e.g., Ogawa et al., 2010; Walter, 2021).

A lithium-ion battery electric vehicle emits 52 percent less CO₂ and a lead-acid battery electric vehicle emits 42 percent less CO₂ in its lifetime compared to a diesel-powered vehicle, despite higher energy consumption in the production of electric vehicles (Table 4; Figure 1). The use of green electricity can further improve the balance of electric vehicles. Lead-acid batteries are almost 100 percent reprocessed and the energy consumption can therefore be estimated as very low. Lithium-ion batteries can be used in a new vehicle or as a stationary storage due to its long service life. In the case of complete dismantling, the study shows a CO₂ value of 15 kg CO₂ / kWh.

Table 4. The CO₂ emissions comparison of the diesel-powered, lead-acid battery and lithium-ion battery forklift trucks with load capacity of 2,5 tons for 10.000 operating hours

CO ₂ emissions for 10.000 operating hours	Diesel-powered forklift truck	Lead-acid battery forklift truck	Lithium-ion battery forklift truck
Forklift truck weight	4.440 kg	2.817 kg	2.817 kg
Conversion factor	1,53 kg CO ₂ / kg	1,53 kg CO ₂ / kg	1,53 kg CO ₂ / kg
Raw materials (Without traction battery)	6,79 tons	4,31 tons	4,31 tons
Battery weight	-	2 x 1.863 kg	-
Energy capacity	-	-	43,2 kWh
Conversion factor	-	1,55 kg CO ₂ / kg	150 kg CO ₂ / kWh
Raw materials (Only traction battery)	-	5,78 tons	6,48 tons
Production / Assembling	0,71 tons	0,18 tons	0,18 tons
Energy consumption	31.000 liters	60.000 kWh	60.000 kWh
Conversion factor	3,177 kg CO ₂ / liter	0,540 kg CO ₂ / kWh	0,540 kg CO ₂ / kWh
Charging factor	-	1,57	1,23
Use phase	98,48 tons	50,87 tons	39,85 tons
Total CO₂	105,98 tons	61,14 tons	50,82 tons
Difference	-	- 42 %	- 52 %

Figure 1. Diesel-powered, lead-acid battery and lithium-ion battery forklift trucks eco-balance

Li-ion batteries are classified as dangerous goods. The disposal route is clearly regulated, the questions of where from and where to are no longer asked in the private sector. Jungheinrich as manufacturer must therefore take back batteries from the customer and is responsible for their correct disposal (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The disposal and recycling of the lithium-ion batteries

Discussion and conclusions

As managerial implications, Jungheinrich is concerned about improving working conditions and ensures that raw materials are not extracted under inhumane conditions by preventing corruption and money laundering, cartel and competition law, data protection and secrecy. Linking own components through software and connectivity increases efficiency and reduces energy consumption of vehicle controls, lithium-ion cells, chargers and battery management systems. The life cycle assessment was certified by the internationally active and recognised service company TÜV Nord. Jungheinrich is the only industrial truck manufacturer to have published a life cycle assessment. It enables Jungheinrich to carry out a CO₂ balance of the vehicle segments. The cell product primarily used at Jungheinrich, the lithium iron phosphate cell chemistry, consists of only 1,4 percent pure lithium.

Lithium is used especially in ceramics and glass, batteries and lubricants. The share of batteries has risen steadily in recent years with 9,5 percent per year, global demand was approximately 34.000 tons in 2013 and 65.000 tons in 2020. In 2013 only 100 Jungheinrich equipment with lithium-ion batteries were sold, 500 in 2015, 6.000 in 2017 and 13.000 in 2018.

Facts about the thesis that there will be no more lithium in 30 years: lithium is a light metal and belongs to the group of alkali metals; share in the earth's crust is 0,006 percent and is slightly rarer than zinc and copper, but slightly more than lead and cobalt; occurrence in minerals, easier extraction; occurrence in brine, more complex extraction. Figures from the US Geological Survey suggest that the world has enormous lithium reserves. At current extraction rates, reserves will last 437 years.

In the lithium extraction is an extremely high consumption of water. The water footprint describes the shares of direct and indirect water consumption of products. The footprint for Germany is 117 billion cubic meters of water per year which means approximately 3.900 litres per day per person. Invisible water load in food and industrial goods: 130 liters of water in one cup of coffee, 3.850 liters of water in a 250 g of steak, 4.100 liters of water in a t-shirt, 8.000 liters of water in a pair of jeans and 7.000 liters of water in a Jungheinrich lithium-ion battery. Lithium-ion batteries have a significantly longer life expectancy than, for example, a pair of jeans or a steak.

The main contributions of this research are related to the importance of the development of the electric forklift trucks refurbishment sector in a post-pandemic period, which helps to reduce resource consumption, extends the life of equipment and offers lower costs for industrial customers, with implications for the final price of consumer goods. The advantages of this research are expressed through the use of lithium-ion battery forklift trucks, which are more energy efficient and offer a 52 percent reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to diesel-powered forklift trucks, due to the lower energy losses within the battery, as opposed to lead-acid batteries, which offer a CO₂ reduction of only 42 percent.

The limitations of this research are related to the fact that the CO₂ emissions analysis methods and results may differ from company to company, the SWOT and ESG analyses represent outdated models and the fact that we did not have access to all internal company documents, some being considered confidential. Future research will focus on expanding electric forklift trucks refurbishment capabilities to other regions and transitioning to lithium-ion batteries, which are sustainable and represent the future of electric forklift trucks evolution.

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